

APPLICATION OF TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE

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ABSTRACT

The traditional knowledge in aquaculture has been predominantly used by the farmers as farm inputs developed by the farmers themselves based on their experiences. Farmer's innovation is based on their indigenous knowledge that finds a wide application in the field of aquaculture and fisheries. Traditional knowledge which can be referred as indigenous knowledge is the accumulated knowledge, skills, and technology of the local farmer resultant from the interaction of the ecosystem. The knowledge has been inherited from generation to generation, finds wide application in some specific location used by specific group of farmers. This drastically minimises the use of drugs, chemicals and fertilizers and formulate some unique thumb rule for disease diagnosis and treatment without the use of costly antibiotics and chemotherapeutic that seriously impacts human health. In many countries of the world, the adaptation of indigenous technologies has resulted in the development of sustainable and environmentally friendly aquaculture practices. Application of paste of turmeric powder and ash of hay or bamboo to control the dreaded fish disease *i. e.* Epizootic Ulcerative Syndrome (EUS) has been practiced by fish farmers of Assam and other North-Eastern States of India. Some farmers even apply branches of Neem plant into fish ponds to control some harmful aquatic insects and pests. Use of a paste made from garlic, salt, CuSO₄ and KMnO₄ mixed in water and sprayed over pond water to control EUS. Banana stem has been used to increase pH of water by cutting them into pieces and immersing in pond water. This practice is also reported to minimize protozoan and argulosis in fish. Periphyton-based food production systems through installing bushy substrates where fish aggregate to breed, feed or shelter has taken advantages by many farmers for ease in harvesting and for better yield. Peels of cucumber or leaves of bitter gourd to control leech, use of paddy straw to control turbidity, use of marigold flower extract for better colorization of ornamental fish, garlic, fenugreek and hing as an fish attractant, use of cattle urine as a potential prophylactic agent against algal bloom etc find wide application in the traditional practices in the aquaculture sector. However, these traditional practices needs further scientific validation and documentation for large scale adoption in the aquaculture sector throughout the country.

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